

Importance of Mental Health

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Abstract:- Mental health has always been an integral part of an individual's overall health and it focuses on an individual's emotional, psychological and social well being. It is equally important for physical well being as well. However, mental health problems are not being reported and are left untreated for the fear of being discriminated against. Depression, anxiety, substance abuse, panic attacks and a lot of other disorders are becoming very common, yet the fear of being judged and the shame that is often associated with discussing psychiatric problems prevents people from talking about it and seeking help for the same. Proper guidance, support and resources are necessary to understand and overcome the mental problems that one is experiencing. Counseling and therapy for mental health problems should be normalized by society rather than looking at it as an abnormality. If left unattended, it will not only impact the person but everyone surrounding and associated with him. There are estimates that tell that 1 in every 5 experience some sort of a mental health condition. One of the major reasons for people not being able to open up about them is the stigma associated with it. Therefore, it is necessary that we understand the importance of mental health and make mental health awareness a priority. This paper is an attempt to make people understand and aware of the importance of mental health. **Mental Health Matters!**

Keywords:- *Mental Health, Integral, Individual well being, Untreated, Discrimination, Psychiatric Problems, Counseling, Therapy, Stigma, Mental Health Awareness, Priority.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Health is defined as a state of physical, social, spiritual and mental well-being. Out of all this, mental health is considered to be the foundation for an individual's overall well-being and the effective functioning of a community as it has an impact on almost everything in life, like education, work, personal relationships, etc. More than 450 million

people suffer from psychological problems and the numbers keep rising everyday. It is estimated that the burden of treating such problems in the future would be associated with high social and economic costs. Treatments for mental health will be way beyond the capacity of both developed and developing countries. Thus, it is better to focus on promoting mental health at the earliest and at the same time preventing and treating mental illness. Mental health is linked to the behavior of people and is fundamental to physical health and the quality of life. Both physical and mental health are interrelated and it is proven that the existence of a mental problem leads to physical complications. It has been proven that depression is one of the major contributors to heart and vascular diseases. Mental disorders affect the health behavior, like regular exercising, eating sensibly, adequate sleep and rest, substance, alcohol and tobacco use, following medical therapies, etc, thus increasing the chances of physical instability. Poor mental health plays a major role in the ineffective functioning of the immune system. On the other hand there are multiple benefits for taking care of mental health namely pleasant mood, reduction of anxiety, creation of an enhanced sense of internal peace, clarity of thoughts, improved relationships and increased self esteem.

It is necessary to take treatments for mental health problems in order to avoid negative consequences and there are a number of therapists and doctors to help, but there is a stigma that is associated with mental illness and it is often the reason why patients are discriminated in the society which eventually leads to a delay in seeking medical expertise. It is often misunderstood that mental problems occur in those who are mentally weak, unstable or are possessed by spirits and are irreversible. The existence of severe social stigma is forcing the affected ones to be reluctant to come out and talk about their problems for the fear of being discriminated against and looked down upon. This makes mental health awareness a major priority, as it is the only way the society can educate itself about mental well being and understand the importance of mental health.

➤ *Objectives*

The aim of this research paper is:

- To increase the society's understanding of mental health
- To reduce the stigma associated with mental and psychological problems
- To foster supportive educational programmes for people struggling with mental problems
- To mobilize efforts in support or favor of mental health

➤ *Scope*

A person's emotional, psychological, and social well-being are all impacted by their mental health, which is a crucial component of total wellbeing. It is the basis for someone being able to live a successful and satisfying life. Mental health conditions can be moderate to severe and significantly affect a person's quality of life. Many variables, including genetics, environment, and life events, might contribute to mental health difficulties.

Four areas have been identified and prioritized to diminish the mental health treatment gap and to increase access to high-quality mental health services globally: diminishing pervasive stigma, building mental health system treatment and research capacity, implementing prevention programs to decrease the incidence of mental disorders, and establishing sustainable scale up of public health systems to improve access to mental health treatment using evidence-based interventions. The main aim of this project is to make people aware of such conditions, to eliminate the stigma associated with discussing such problems and to seek help for the treatment of mental conditions.

➤ *Statement of Problem :*

Mental health concerns are frequently stigmatized, and there are little services available despite the tremendous effects that mental health has on people and communities. People may feel humiliated or embarrassed to ask for help since mental health problems are sometimes viewed as a sign of weakness. In addition, many people frequently lack access to or cannot afford mental health care, especially those who live in low-income areas.

It is extremely important to emphasize the significance of mental health as an individual's capacity to work, establish and maintain relationships, and lead a satisfying life can all be negatively impacted by poor mental health. Families and communities may also be impacted by mental health difficulties, which may also have an influence on healthcare expenses, social results, and productivity. The negative consequences associated with ignoring mental

problems are too huge to be borne. Thus, this topic is of immense importance and proper education on it would help make the lives of a vast population easier.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

In this Literature Review we examine the existing literature on the challenges faced by people regarding their mental health and the potential to increase awareness among people regarding their mental health.

A review by Dr Ursula M (2012) found that mental health care is a neglected area in Ghana and there is no knowledge of psychiatric illness in this country and there are no outcomes for treatment as well. It suggests that there are furthermore important areas of future research which require intervention in health care.

A review by Farzida Karim (Cureus -2020) found that social media was responsible for increasing mental health problems and have concluded that prolonged use of social media sites may lead to negative signs and symptoms among people like anxiety , depression ,stress etc. It has a detrimental effect on the psychological health of its users and further research would prevent suicides from occurring.

A review by Mike Slade(2010) found that we'll – being of people should be promoted rather than treating illness which involves incorporating emerging knowledge from recovery and positive psychology into education and training for all mental health professional s.

A review by Sanjana Bhakta (2021) found out how data helps in prioritising that mental health services and resources are available to meet mental health needs to identify specific needs within communities and its impact of education programs like MHFA(Mental Health first Aid)

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology used to complete this paper is Secondary Data analysis. Secondary data is the data that has been already collected by researchers using primary sources of data collection. The reason for choosing this research methodology is because secondary data is readily available. It makes the research work easier, less time consuming and more cost effective. The methods used in this paper for collecting secondary data are online research papers and articles, books and magazines from educational institutions, university published studies and encyclopedias.

➤ *Data Analysis and Interpretation*

Table 1 Data Analysis and Interpretation

Disorder	Share of global population with disorder (2017) [difference across countries]	Number of people with the disorder (2017)	Share of males:females with disorder (2017)
Any mental health disorder	10.7%	792 million	9.3% males 11.9% females
Depression	3.4% [2-6%]	264 million	2.7% males 4.1% females
Anxiety disorders	3.8% [2.5-7%]	284 million	2.8% males 4.7% females
Bipolar disorder	0.6% [0.3-1.2%]	46 million	0.55% males 0.65% females
Eating disorders (clinical anorexia & bulimia)	0.2% [0.1-1%]	16 million	0.13% males 0.29% females
Schizophrenia	0.3% [0.2-0.4%]	20 million	0.26% males 0.25% females
Any mental or substance use disorder	13% [11-18%]	970 million	12.6% males 13.3% females
Alcohol use disorder	1.4% [0.5-5%]	107 million	2% males 0.8% females
Drug use disorder (excluding alcohol)	0.9% [0.4-3.5%]	71 million	1.3% males

This data represents the latest estimates of the prevalent mental disorders and their burden. This study was conducted in the year 2017 and it was estimated that a total of 792 million people were suffering from mental health problems. Despite such large numbers being reported, it has been proven that mental health disorders are still underreported. It is very necessary to keep in mind that the uncertainty of the data available regarding mental health is too high, thus researchers should be extremely cautious when interpreting changes over time. The data mentioned in this paper shows us that mental health disorders are very common and are increasing worldwide.

WHO has reported that there has been a 13% rise in mental health problems and substance abuse (2017). About 20% of the world's adolescents and children have been

diagnosed with mental health problems. All this has led to suicide becoming the second largest cause of death among the youth. Mental health has an impact on everything ranging from school, college, work to family, friendships and relationships. Despite these alarming numbers and figures, the share of expenditure that goes to mental health related problems out of the global average of government health expenditure is reported to be less than 2%.

Thus it is very important to increase awareness, improve recognition, support and treatment for mental health disorders. It is necessary to make common people and the authorities understand the impacts of mental health problems and the consequences associated with them if not treated properly.

More students seeking mental health support

Number of students who accessed treatment during the year

Fig 1 Analysis reveals that over the past five years, there has been more than a 50% rise in the number of students seeking mental health care while being enrolled in universities.

Fig 2 According to the Department for Education, Colleges Must Offer Pastoral Care to Students

- The number of students seeking assistance for mental health difficulties increased by 53% during the course of the five academic years from 2012 to 2017—from 50,901 to 78,061.
- The overall funding for university mental health services increased by 43% from £25.5 million in 2012–13 to £36.6 million in 2016–17.
- Throughout the same five years, there has been a 1% decrease in the student population.

Although most of the students are making an effort to get mental health services, some still face obstacles because of structural problems and the stigma associated with discussing mental health issues.

IV. DISCUSSION

It is impossible to overestimate the importance of one of the most significant contributors to the overall well-being of an individual, that is Mental health. Those with sound mental health can live satisfactory lives, manage their everyday troubles, and keep up positive connections. On the other hand, those with poor mental health can be negatively impacted as a result of it, which can cause a number of issues with both their mental and physical stability.

The significance of mental health can be attributed to a number of factors. First of all, Mental health has a major impact on people's feelings, thought process and their actions. The daily lives of most individuals are influenced by their thoughts and emotions, which will be much easier to control when they maintain a good mental health. Secondly, both physical and mental well being are interconnected. It has been proven that mental health conditions like depression, anxiety and stress can also be possible reasons for major physical health problems like diabetes, strokes and cardiovascular diseases. Thirdly, interpersonal interactions or the way people communicate with others is highly impacted by their mental health. They can develop and retain healthy relationships with their family, friends and colleagues when their mental health is in a good condition. It also makes people capable of resolving their own problems, analyzing what others are going

through, empathizing with them and communicating clearly in order to eradicate the misunderstanding.

Finally, mental health also impacts an individuals' work and productivity. Their capacity to concentrate, make choices from alternatives and their ability to perform well at work can all be negatively impacted by poor mental health. Added to that, it may lead to increased absenteeism, decreased productivity and extremely low levels of work performance. Ultimately, good mental health is the main contributor to a high quality life. It makes it possible for people to enjoy life, take part in worthwhile activities, and to chase their dreams.

V. FINDINGS

According to our research, having good mental health is very crucial for the overall wellbeing of an individual. Key findings from our research on mental health include the following points:

- Physical and mental health are interconnected: Poor mental health is highly likely to become the cause of physical health disorders like diabetes, strokes and cardiovascular diseases.
- Mental Health has an impact on work productivity: Mental health conditions can have a major impact on the output and performance at work. Employees or workers with poor mental health may show signs of increased absenteeism, decreased productivity and less likely to be satisfied with their job.
- 3.Mental health has a significant impact on personal connections: Family, friendships, and romantic relationships can all be affected by mental health conditions. Individuals with poor mental health may find it extremely difficult to establish and retain their connections, which can result in them feeling lonely and secluded.
- Academic performance of students is also impacted by mental health: Students who display signs of depression and anxiety are more likely to perform poorly and to experience academic failures.

VI. CONCLUSION

The state of an individual's mental health has a major impact on all the other factors of their life, including their physical well being, professional work, connections and relationships. A diverse variety of issues, such as troubled functioning, an increased risk of physical sickness, and a decreased quality of life, can all be possible conditions brought about by poor mental health.

On the other hand, being of sound mental health has a lot of advantages like increased happiness and satisfaction, better coping mechanisms, and better overall functioning of the individual.

It is extremely important to prioritize mental health for all the reasons mentioned above, and that requires understanding the importance of and engaging in self care activities, proper treatments, regular exercises and social support. The stigma associated with discussing mental problems has not been completely eradicated but it is definitely better than what it was a few years before. The value of mental health in society as a whole is becoming increasingly recognised, even in terms of policies and decision-making. Increased funding is being provided by government authorities and NGOs for mental health services, research and mental awareness is the result of this acknowledgment. In conclusion, mental health is one such important factor that should be promoted and supported on a personal as well as societal level because it is one of the most critical components and contributors for the overall well being and functioning of an individual.

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